

ELASTIC MODULUS OF AN ALUMINIUM-BASED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE REINFORCED WITH α -ALUMINA PLATELETS : EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The Young modulus of an aluminium-based metal matrix composite reinforced with α -alumina platelets was investigated from an experimental and a theoretical point of view by varying the following parameters : nature of the matrix, morphology and volume fraction of the platelets. An iterative Eshelby method, taking into account different families of inclusions, was used to perform the theoretical predictions. A good agreement between theory and experience was observed.

Lastly, to assess the effectiveness of the platelets as reinforcing phases, a comparison with the values of the Young moduli obtained theoretically with other shapes of reinforcement (spheres or short fibers) was carried out.

Keywords : aluminium matrix composite, α -alumina platelets, Young modulus, iterative Eshelby method

1. INTRODUCTION

The improvement of the mechanical properties of particulate metal matrix composites is closely related to the introduction in a ductile matrix of ceramic particles, the thermal and mechanical properties of which are quite different from the properties of the matrix material in which they are inserted. The shape of the particulates used as a reinforcement (spheres, short fibers or platelets) and their characteristics (elastic constants and coefficient of thermal expansion, for example) can have a great influence on the level of strengthening obtained.

This study will be focussed on the Young modulus of an aluminium-based MMC reinforced with α -alumina platelets, several microstructural parameters of which such as the nature of the matrix or the adjustable parameters of the reinforcing phases were successively investigated.

The aim of this paper is to establish a correlation between the experimental values of Young modulus and the theoretical evolutions predicted by a model based on an iterative Eshelby method developed by Hamann et al [1]. The advantage of this iterative method in comparison with most other models based on the Eshelby analysis is the fact that the reinforcing phases can be represented by several types of ellipsoidal inclusions. The elastic constants, the shape, the volume fraction and the orientation of each type of inclusion can be adjustable and may vary from one type of inclusion to another.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The composite on which this study is focussed is an aluminium-based MMC reinforced with preforms of α -alumina platelets. The preforms elaborated by Elf-Atochem consist of randomly oriented hexagonal and monocrystalline platelets, as shown in figure 1.

The size of the platelets, which is defined by two parameters : a diameter (d) and a thickness (t), may vary depending on the synthesis conditions, as can be seen in table 1. However, with all sizes of platelets, the aspect ratio (t / d) ranges from 1/20 to 1/10. Independently of the size of the platelets, the volume fraction of the preforms may vary between 15% and 35%.

Figure 1 : Monocrystalline hexagonal α -alumina platelets

Type of platelets	Diameter d (μm)	Thickness t (μm)	Mean aspect ratio (t/d)
T1	5 - 10	0,5	1/15
T2	10 - 15	1,0	1/12,5
T3	15 - 25	1,2	1/16,5

Table 1 : Definition of the different types of platelets

By using different types of preforms constituted with various volume fractions of platelets of different sizes and two aluminium matrixes (either a commercially pure aluminium matrix (99,9 % Al) or a 6061 aluminium matrix (1% Magnesium, 0,6% Silicon)), composite materials were elaborated by the squeeze-casting technique. The 6061 matrix composites were submitted to a T6 thermal heat treatment .

The combination of different types of preforms with the two aluminium matrixes allowed us to study the influence on the Young modulus of the variable parameters of the material.

2.2 Experimental procedure

The Young moduli were essentially measured by extensometry during tensile tests. However, to confirm these results, a few dynamic measurements were performed additionally. The dynamic moduli were obtained from the mechanical resonance frequency of a parallelepipedic composite bar. In this paper, we will refer to the values of static moduli, knowing that the two types of measurements of Young moduli led us to the same conclusions. We only observed that there was a small difference (not exceeding 5%) between the static and dynamic values, the dynamic moduli being higher than the static moduli.

3. THE ITERATIVE ESHELBY METHOD

3.1 Principle

The iterative Eshelby method developed by Hamann et al [1] allows us to calculate the elastic constants of a composite reinforced with several families of inclusions, each family being characterized by a representative inclusion defined by its thermoelastic constants, its shape (aspect ratio) and its orientation in fixed axes related to the composite. A volume fraction is associated with each family.

Each representative inclusion is considered as a single inclusion in an infinite matrix.

The principle of the calculations by the iterative method can be described as follows :

When the system (single inclusion in an infinite matrix) is thermally or mechanically loaded, incompatibilities of deformation between the two constituents generate stresses in and around the inclusion. The level of these stresses depends on the microstructural parameters of the system and can be assessed by using the Eshelby method in the case of ellipsoidal inclusions. At each step of the calculation, for each family, the basic concept of the Eshelby theory is used to obtain :

- the equivalent stress free strain $[\epsilon^{Teq,I}]$ expressed as a function of the applied stress field $[\sigma^A]$ and of the transformation stress free strain of the representative inclusion $[\epsilon^{T^*,I}]$
- the internal stress field in the single inclusion $[\sigma^{Inc,I}]$ expressed as a function of $[\epsilon^{Teq,I}]$

The local effect of the surrounding inclusions (image field) cannot be easily evaluated (the stresses are constant in the inclusions but not in the matrix) but the mean value of this contribution over the total volume of the composite $\langle[\sigma^{im}] \rangle$ is given by the following expression resulting from the equilibrium conditions :

$$\langle[\sigma^{im}] \rangle = - \sum_I f_I \cdot [\sigma^{Inc,I}]$$

where $[\sigma^{Inc,I}]$ is the stress in the representative inclusion of the family referenced I and f_I is the volume fraction attributed to this family. The total mean image stress field is obtained by adding the contribution of each family considered independently from the others. At the next step of the calculation, $\langle[\sigma^{im}] \rangle$ is considered as a contribution to the external stress field and is added to it to evaluate a corrective term $\Delta\langle[\sigma^{im}] \rangle$. The total mean image stress field is then calculated after several iterations. When a convergence criterion is satisfied (*), the strain and stress state of the composite is determined. Finally, the elastic moduli can be calculated once the composite strain $[\epsilon^A]$, related to the applied and internal stress fields, has been evaluated.

* Mori and Wakashima [2] demonstrated the convergence of the value of the mean image stress and of the stresses in the inclusions in the case of a composite reinforced with a single type of inclusion

3.2 Application to the case of the composite investigated

In the particular case of the composite studied, the theoretical calculations of Young moduli were performed in the following conditions :

- 1- The reinforcement was simulated by representative inclusions characterized by the same elastic constants, the same ellipsoidal shape but by different orientations
- 2- Oblate spheroids of aspect ratio $a_3 / a_1 = t / d$ were used to represent the platelets, as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 : Simulation of the morphology of the platelets by oblate spheroids

3- No distribution of aspect ratio was taken into account in the calculations. This is supported by the fact that the aspect ratio distribution of the platelets around their mean aspect ratio is narrow. On the other hand, it has been shown that there is no significant difference between the modulus of a composite, the particles of which have the same aspect ratio (undistributed case) and the one of a composite characterized by an equally reparted distribution of aspect ratios around the same mean value [1].

4- The orientation of the representative inclusions in fixed axes linked to the composite is defined by two angles Zeta (ζ) and Alpha (α), as shown in figure 3. The values of Zeta and Alpha were chosen in such a way that a random (or isotropic) orientation of the platelets in the composite can be studied (figure 4).

To account for such a configuration of orientation of the reinforcement, nine families of oblate spheroids (having the same elastic constants and the same aspect ratio but various orientations) were sufficient and allowed us to ensure a correct simulation of an isotropic material.

5- The volume fraction f_i attributed to each family was $f_i = F/N$ where F is the total volume fraction of the platelets in the composite and N is the number of families.

Figure 3 : Definition of the Zeta and Alpha angles

Figure 4 : Random orientation of the platelets in the composite

6- The platelets used in this study are single crystals of α -alumina, the structure of which is trigonal. As a result, they present a certain degree of elastic anisotropy [3]. However, in all simulations, the representative inclusions were assumed elastically isotropic. They were thus defined by two parameters : a Young modulus (E) and a Poisson's ratio (ν). This was done keeping in mind that the platelets are randomly oriented, leading to a macroscopically isotropic material. Referring to the data of the literature relative to α -alumina reinforcements [3,4], we chose the following values for the elastic constants of the representative inclusions :

---> Young modulus : $E=380$ GPa

---> Poisson's ratio $\nu=0,25$

These values are generally attributed to a fully dense, isotropic, polycrystalline alumina ceramic body. We will in a next paragraph discuss the ability of these values to simulate our composite.

4. RESULTS

In this section, we will successively review the effect predicted by the iterative method on the Young modulus of :

---> the Young modulus of the matrix

---> the aspect ratio and the volume fraction of the platelets represented by oblate spheroids in the particular case of a random orientation of the reinforcing phases.

As far as possible, a comparison with the experimental values will be made in order to relate the experimental results with the theoretical evolutions.

To conclude our study, we will theoretically assess the effect of the shape of the reinforcing phases (spheres, short fibers or platelets) on the Young modulus of a metal matrix composite .

4.1 Correlation between theoretical and experimental results

In the experimental and theoretical parametric study mentioned above, a single parameter to be focussed on was used as a variable whereas the remaining parameters were set equal to their typical values shown in table 2.

Parameter	Typical value
Young modulus of the matrix	$E_m=69$ GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu=0,33$
Aspect ratio of the oblate spheroids : a_3/a_1	1/15
Volume fraction of the oblate spheroids	20%

Table 2 : Typical values of the parameters

4.1.1 Preliminary study : validation of the choice of the elastic constants of the reinforcement

The study of the effect of the Young modulus of the matrix was used to justify the choice of the elastic constants chosen for the alumina platelets.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of the Young modulus of a composite (E_c) reinforced with randomly oriented oblate spheroids as a function of the Young modulus of the matrix (E_m). A linear dependance is observed, the law of evolution being : $E_c=1,107.E_m + 26,4$

Our own results showed us that the nature of the matrix (pure aluminium or 6061 alloy) had a great influence on the Young modulus of the composite. It can only be attributed to a difference between the Young modulus of both matrixes, the other parameters being the same. The data of the literature [5] confirmed by our own experimental results led us to a modulus of 69 GPa for the 6061 alloy and of 62 GPa for pure aluminium. As shown in table 3, with such values of Young moduli, a very good correlation is observed between the experimental and theoretical results. In particular, it should be noticed that the experimental and theoretical ratios defined by $E_{(6061/Al_2O_3)} / E_{(Al/Al_2O_3)}$ are very close.

Composite	Experimental Young modulus (GPa)	Theoretical Young modulus (GPa)
6061/Al ₂ O ₃	104	102,8
Al/Al ₂ O ₃	95	95

Table 3 : Effect of the Young modulus of the matrix

As mentioned above, the elastic constants of the alumina inclusions were chosen referring to the data of the literature for an isotropic polycrystalline alumina, that is to say relatively arbitrarily. As a consequence, in order to ascertain that the evolutions predicted by the model are not dependant on the elastic constants chosen for the reinforcement, we plotted in figure 6 the evolution of the Young modulus of a 6061 or a pure aluminium matrix composite as a function of the Young modulus of the alumina particles (in the range of possible values for a single crystal of alumina). It is clear that the model accounts for the experimental results since the ratio $E_{(6061/Al_2O_3)} / E_{(Al/Al_2O_3)}$ remains the same, whatever the Young modulus. Lastly, we will notice that the elastic constants, which were chosen for the representative inclusions, allows us to fit particularly well the experimental results. They will be used in the next paragraphs to carry out the calculations.

Figure 5 : Evolution of the Young modulus of the composite with the Young modulus of the matrix

Figure 6 : Evolution of the Young modulus of the composite with the Young modulus of the alumina reinforcement

4.1.2 Effect of the aspect ratio of the reinforcement

Figure 7 is the representation of the evolution of the Young modulus of a composite (E_c) reinforced with randomly oriented oblate spheroids as a function of their aspect ratio. It appears that there is a strong decrease in the Young modulus of the composite with the aspect ratio, particularly when it does not exceed 1/5. Above this value, the influence of the aspect ratio appears as being quasi negligible.

The platelets used in this study (whatever their size) have a mean aspect ratio which varies between 1/20 and 1/10. In this range of values, the aspect ratio on the modulus has a great effect. We have thus measured the Young moduli of composites reinforced with the same volume fraction of platelets of different types (see table 1). The experimental values are plotted in figure 6. We observe a good agreement between the experiment and the theory with the platelets referenced T1 and T2. The discrepancy observed in the case of the largest platelets (T3) could be attributed to a less homogeneous distribution of these platelets in the composite. It is supported by the fact that pile ups of platelets have been observed, which could lead to an increase in the real aspect ratio of the reinforcement and subsequently to a decrease in the Young modulus.

4.1.3 Effect of the volume fraction of reinforcement

In figure 8, we reported the theoretical evolution of the Young modulus of a composite (E_c) reinforced with randomly oriented oblate spheroids as a function of their volume fraction as well as the experimental evolution determined on 6061 matrix composites. In both cases, a linear dependance of the Young modulus with the volume fraction is observed in the range of values investigated experimentally (between 20% and 35 % of reinforcement), the law of evolution being :

a) from the results of the theoretical study : $E_c = 198,8.F + 63,2$

b) from the results of the experimental study : $E_c = 203.F + 63,3$

A very good correlation between theory and experience appears once more, which validates as well the model as the choice of the elastic constants.

Figure 7 : Evolution of the Young modulus of the composite with the aspect ratio of the platelets represented by oblate spheroids

Figure 8 : Evolution of the Young modulus of the composite with the volume fraction of the platelets represented by oblate spheroids

4.2 Study of the effect of the shape of the reinforcing phases on the Young modulus of the composite

As noticed above, the morphology of the reinforcement has a significant effect on the modulus. In this section, we will consider the influence of the shape of the inclusions on the modulus, assuming isotropic elastic constants for the reinforcement.

In addition to the case of oblate spheroids, we will study the case where the inclusions have the shape : either of spheres or of prolate spheroids defined by $a_1=a_2$ and $a_3 > a_1$. The prolate spheroids can simulate short fibers for example.

In order to establish the shape of the reinforcing phases (spheres, short fibers or platelets) which would best obtain a high modulus, we calculated by the iterative method the modulus of a composite reinforced with a volume fraction F of spheres (S) or of prolate spheroids (P.S.) or of oblate spheroids (O.S.).

Our calculations were carried out considering that the matrix is a 6061 alloy. The elastic constants of the reinforcement were set equal to the values taken in the preceding calculations.

In all simulations, we chose a mean aspect ratio equal to 15 for the prolate spheroids and to 1/15 for the oblate spheroids.

Two configurations of orientation of the reinforcing phases were studied : a random orientation and a perfect alignment of the reinforcement in one direction (the isotropy in the transversal plane being conserved).

As the effect studied is only a geometrical one, we compared the values of the Young moduli (E) obtained with the different shapes of particles with the ones (E_s) calculated in the case of spheres of same elastic constants and same volume fraction. In figures 9 and 10, we thus reported the evolution of the ratio E/E_s as a function of the volume fraction.

In the case of a random orientation of the particulates (figure 9), it clearly appears that it is more advantageous, in order to obtain a high modulus, to use reinforcing phases having the shape of platelets (oblate spheroids) rather than short fibers (prolate spheroids) or spheres.

On the contrary, when the reinforcement is aligned along one direction (figure 10), short fibers lead to a higher longitudinal modulus (E_l) than platelets. However, it should be noticed that this advantage is counterbalanced by the fact that the transversal modulus (E_t) is smaller with short fibers than with platelets.

Figure 9: Random orientation of the reinforcing phases. Effect of the shape of the particulates on the Young modulus of the composite

Figure 10 : Alignment of the reinforcing phases in a direction. Effect of the shape of the particulates on the longitudinal and transversal Young moduli of the composite

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper showed the influence of several microstructural parameters on the Young modulus of a metal matrix composite reinforced with α -alumina platelets. The main conclusions of our study can be summed up as follows :

- 1- A good agreement was found between the experimental values and the predictions of the iterative Eshelby method which allowed us to take into account all the parameters studied
- 2- One of the major interests of the morphology of the platelets used lies in their small aspect ratio which places them in the range of values where the elastic moduli are high.
- 3- On the other hand, in comparison with other types of reinforcement (spheres or short fibers), the shape of platelets appears to be more favourable if a good compromise between the values of longitudinal, isotropic and transversal moduli is wanted.

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